

Synthesis and Antimicrobial Activity of some 1,2,4-Triazoles

EL SAYED H EL-TAMANY*, MOHY EL-DIN ABD EL-FATTAH, IBRAHIM A IBRAHIM and EZZ EL-DIN M. SALEM

Chemistry Department, Faculty of Science, Suez Canal University, Ismailha, Egypt

Manuscript received 15 February 1996, revised 26 August 1996, accepted 19 November 1996

The addition and alkylation reactions of the triazole (1) have been studied. The products obtained are used in the synthesis of new derivatives. The complexation of amide (2b) with some metal cations is also described. All the compounds have been tested against some bacteria and fungi to evaluate their biological actions.

Triazoles, in general, possess wide biological activities¹. Therefore, the conjugation of the antimicrobial agent *p*-chlorophenoxyacetic acid with thiotriazole could afford interesting series of compounds having potent biological activities. This communication deals with the synthesis of derivatives of 3-*p*-chlorophenoxymethyl-4-phenyl-5-thio-1,2,4 triazole (1) and screening their antimicrobial activity against some bacteria and fungi. The starting compound 1

underwent Michael addition reaction with acrylonitrile, acrylamide and methyl acrylate to yield the corresponding β -triazole-1-ylpropionitrile (2a), propionamide (2b) and methyl β -triazole-1-ylpropionate (2c) (Scheme 1; Table 1). The participation of NH in the addition reaction rather than SH group was established from ¹H nmr spectra, which displayed signals at δ 4.5–4.6 attributable to (t, 2H, NCH₂CH₂), which is in agreement with the reported data

by Amico *et al.*^{6,7} on related compounds. Surprisingly enough, treatment of the nitrile (**2a**) with sodium hydroxide led to its cleavage to the starting triazole (**1**) instead of the formation of the expected free acid.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 2–17*

Compd. no	M p.** °C	Spectral data
2a	125 ^a	ν_{\max} 2 247 cm^{-1} (C≡N), $\delta(\text{CDCl}_3)$ 7 5–6 6 (9H, m, ArH), 4 9 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 4 45 (2H, t, N- CH ₂), 2 88 (2H, t, CH ₂ CN)
2b	130 ^a	ν_{\max} 3 409 (NH ₂), 1 678 cm^{-1} (C=O, amide); m/z 388 (M ⁺ , 36), 317 (15), 276 (30), 261 (84), 190 (100), 77 (44)
2c	76 ^a	ν_{\max} 1 726 (C=O ester), 1 287 cm^{-1} (C=S), $\delta(\text{CDCl}_3)$ 7 6–6 7 (9H, m, ArH), 4 9 (2H, s, OCH ₃), 4 6 (2H, t, NCH ₂ CH ₂), 3 7 (3H, s, CH ₃), 3 0 (2H, t, NCH ₂ CH ₂)
3	175 ^b	ν_{\max} 3 080 (NH), 1 588 (C=N), 1 273 cm^{-1} (N=N-N), m/z 388 (M ⁺ -HCN), 371 (M-N ₃), 370 (M ⁺ -HN ₃)
4a	82 ^b	ν_{\max} 3 305 (NH), 1 640 cm^{-1} (C=O)
4b	175 ^a	ν_{\max} 3 195 (NH), 1 600 cm^{-1} (C=O)
5	80 ^a	ν_{\max} 3 305 (NH), 1 639 (C=O), 1 286 (C=S)
6	120 ^c	ν_{\max} 3 400 (OH), 1 716 cm^{-1} (C=O acid)
7	143 ^a	ν_{\max} 3 327, 3 290 (NH ₂ , NH), 1 665 (C=O), 1 348 cm^{-1} (C=S)
8a	73 ^a	ν_{\max} 3 397 (NH), 1 695 cm^{-1} (C=O)
8b	183 ^a	ν_{\max} 3 320 (NH), 1 685 cm^{-1} (C=O); $\delta(\text{CDCl}_3)$, 8.7 (1H, s N=C-H), 7.8–6.7 (13H, m, ArH), 4 8 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 4 7 (2H, t, N- CH ₂ CH ₂), 3 4 (2H, t, N-C ₂ CH ₂), m/z 526 (M ⁺ , 10), 318 (2), 276 (12), 178 (44), 137 (100), 76 (93)
8c	125 ^a	ν_{\max} 3 357 (NH), 1 602 cm^{-1} (C=O)
8d	285 ^d	ν_{\max} 3 397 (NH), 1 670 cm^{-1} (C=O)
9	78 ^a	ν_{\max} 3 217 (NH), 1 604 (C=O), 1 347 cm^{-1} (C=S)
10a	55 ^a	$\delta(\text{CDCl}_3)$ 7 6–6 7 (9H, m, ArH), 6 0–5 85 (1H, m, CH ₂ CH=CH ₂), 5 2 (2H, d, CH ₂ CH=C(H) ₂), 5 0 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 4 0 (2H, d, SCH ₂); m/z 357 (M ⁺ , 5), 295 (11), 230 (100), 149 (99), 129 (83), 57 (30)

Table-1(Contd)

10b	126 ^a	ν_{\max} 3 318 (NH ₂), 1 675 (C=O), 1 601 cm^{-1} (C=N)
10c	165 ^b	ν_{\max} 3 428 (OH), 1 690 (C=O acid), $\delta(\text{CDCl}_3)$ 7 6–6 8 (9H, m, ArH), 5 0 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 4 0 (2H, s, SCH ₂), m/z 376 (M ⁺ , 3), 317 (47), 248 (100), 190 (31)
10d	95	-
12	155 ^a	ν_{\max} 3 191 (NH), 1 697 (C=O), 1 314 cm^{-1} (C=S)
13	175 ^a	ν_{\max} 3 193 (NH), 1 600 cm^{-1} (C=O), m/z 493 (M ⁺ , 2), 479 (3), 431 (6), 332 (8), 285 (11), 225 (14), 191 (20), 149 (100), 77 (75)
14	120 ^c	ν_{\max} 3 180 (NH) 1 650 cm^{-1} (C=O)
15a	59 ^b	ν_{\max} 3 303 (NH), 1 695 cm^{-1} (C=O), $\delta(\text{CDCl}_3)$ 7 5–6 6 (9H, m, ArH), 5 0 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 4.5 (1H, d, C'HCH(CH ₂) ₂), 4 2 (2H, q, OCH ₂ - CH ₂), 4 0 (2H, s, SCH ₂), 2 55 (1H, m, C'H(CH ₂) ₂), 1 25 (3H, t, CH ₃), 0 9 (6H, d, CH ₂ (CH ₂) ₂)
15b	110 ^a	ν_{\max} 3 474 (OH), 3 287 (NH), 1 677 cm^{-1} (C=O)
15c	200 ^a	ν_{\max} 3 480 (OH), 3 440 (NH), 1 731 cm^{-1} (C=O, acid), m/z 433 (M ⁺ , 1), 376 (2), 317 (34), 190 (100), 77 (34)
15d	180 ^a	ν_{\max} 3 474 (OH), 3 440 (NH), 1 700 cm^{-1} (C=O)
16	75 ^a	ν_{\max} 3 151 (NH ₂), 1 598 cm^{-1} (C=N); m/z 431 (M ⁺ , 2), 382 (7), 319 (20), 192 (19), 149 (83), 131 (100), 77 (25)
17	185 ^a	ν_{\max} 3 260 (NH ₂) 1 623 (C=N), 1 307 cm^{-1} (C=S), $\delta(\text{CDCl}_3)$ 7 6– 6 7 (9H, m, ArH), 5 5 (2H, s, NH ₂), 5 0 (2H, s, OCH ₂), 4.5 (2H, s, SCH ₂)

*Elemental analyses of compounds gave satisfactory results

**Solvent for crystallisation : ^aEtOH, ^bEtOH-H₂O, ^cH₂O, ^dBuOH-light petrol (b.p 60–80°), ^eacetone

Meanwhile, compound **2a** underwent partial hydrolysis to the corresponding amide (**2b**) by boiling with HOAc/HCl mixture. Compound **2a** on treatment with sodium azide/ammonium chloride afforded the tetrazolotriazole (**3**). An attempt to acylate the amide (**2b**) with benzoyl chloride failed to give the corresponding N-acyl derivative. However, the reaction proceeded with dehydration of **2b** to the corresponding nitrile (**2a**). Mannich reaction was carried out on **2b** to furnish the N-piperidino/morpholino methyl derivatives (**4a,b**). On the other hand, the reaction of **2b** with phenyl isothiocyanate gave the thiourea derivative (**5**). Ester **2c** underwent alkaline hydrolysis and hydrazinolysis to the corresponding acid (**6**) and hydrazide (**7**) respectively.

Arylidene derivatives (**8a-d**) were obtained by condensing **7** with some aromatic aldehydes according to the conventional methods. Reaction of the hydrazide (**7**) with phenyl isothiocyanate afforded the thiosemicarbazide derivative (**9**). An attempt to carry out a reaction between the triazole (**1**) and allyl bromide failed to give the Michael addition product, and instead it underwent S-alkylation affording the allylthioether derivative (**10a**). The structure of **10a** was assigned by ^1H nmr data which revealed doublet corresponding to $\text{SCH}_2\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$ ($\delta 4.0$). Other S-alkylation reactions of **1** were carried out by treating with a variety of alkylating agents in the presence of triethylamine or sodium hydroxide. However, the synthesis of the alkyl derivative (**10b-d**) and the hydrazide (**11**) have been published elsewhere³. The hydrazide (**11**) reacted with phenyl isothiocyanate, benzoyl chloride and benzene sulphonylchloride to give the corresponding derivatives **12-14** according to the conventional methods. It may be mentioned that the free acid carboxymethylthiotriazolyl derivative (**10c**) has valuable synthetic applications. It is well known that the introduction of amino acids to antimicrobial agents could afford more potent and less toxic products⁴. Therefore, the free acid (**10c**) was coupled with DL-valine ethylester in the presence of dicyclohexyl carbodiimide to afford the ester (**15a**).

Reaction of **10c** with L-leucine by the mixed anhydride method and with glycine or 6-aminopenicillanic acid (6-APA) by the acid chloride procedure at pH 8-9 led to the formation of the corresponding amino acid derivative (**15b-d**). Cycloaddition of **10c** by reaction with thiosemicarbazide in the presence of POCl_3 led to the aminothiazolyl derivative (**16**), whereas on fusion with thiocarbonylhydrazide yielded the aminotriazole derivative (**17**). It has been established that metal complexes possess enhanced and superior biological activity than the parent ligand⁵. Therefore, some complexes of the amide **2b** were prepared as representative of this series of compounds. This selection was based on the importance of amide function not only for exhibiting high level of activity but also for the facile formation of metal complexes. Treatment of **2b** with metal salts of copper, cobalt, nickel and zinc in boiling alcohol gave solid complexes, where the metal/ligand ratio was found to be 1 : 1 by titrating against EDTA using murexide or eriochrome black T. Ir spectra of the isolated complexes revealed the participation of the carbonyl and thiocarbonyl groups in the complex formation (Table 2).

Biological activity : Using disc-diffusion technique⁶, all the newly compounds were tested *in vitro* against some strains of bacteria such as *Escherichia coli*, *Proteus sp.* and *Bacillus subtilis*, and fungi such as *Aspergillus sydowii*, *Fusarium oxysporum* and *Penicillium sp.* at concentrations 100 and 1000 ppm. The results indicated that some com-

pounds are active towards gram-positive bacteria (**4a** and CuL complex) and some towards gram-positive and gram-negative (CuL, ZnL, NiL complexes). Compounds **4a**, **5**, **8c**, **9**, **12**, **14**, CuL, CoL, ZnL complexes showed moderate antifungal activity. This study shows the necessity for extending the study of the metal complexes to include other elements and other ligands from this series to screen their antimicrobial action.

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF THE METAL COMPLEXES (ML)

Compd	Mol. formula/(mol wt.) Colour, M p °C	Metal% (Found/Calcd.)	ν_{max} (cm^{-1})
CuL	$\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{23}\text{ClN}_4\text{O}_6\text{SCu}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ Blue, 185d	10.79 (10.80)	3413–3370 (H_2O), 1643 (C=O), 1217 (C=S), 544 (M–O), 469 (M–S)
CoL	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2\text{Cl}_3\text{Co}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ Black, 298d	11.90 (11.00)	1659 (C=O), 1249 (C=S), 518 (M–O), 497 (M–S)
NiL	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{Cl}_2\text{N}_4\text{O}_2\text{SNi}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ Green, >350	12.36 (11.80)	3439–3308 (H_2O), 1660 (C=O), 1224 (C=S), 518 (M–O), 418 (M–S)
ZnL	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{Cl}_2\text{N}_4\text{O}_2\text{SZn}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ White, 173d	13.34 (12.95)	3431–3218 (H_2O), 1660 (C=O), 1239 (C=S), 540 (M–O), 475 (M–S)

Experimental

M.p.s. were measured on a Mel-TempII apparatus and are uncorrected. Infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 1340 spectrophotometer, ^1H nmr spectra on a Varian-Gemini (200 MHz) spectrometer and mass spectra on a GC-MSQP 1000 EX Shimadzu instrument.

(A) *Michael addition products and their derivatives* :

Reaction of 3-p-chlorophenoxyethyl-4-phenyl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole (1) with some unsaturated conjugated compounds. Formation of 2a-c. General method : To a solution of triazole **1** (3.17g, 0.01 mol) in ethanol (40 ml), α,β -unsaturated compounds (acrylonitrile, acrylamide and methyl acrylate; 0.015 mol) and triethylamine (2.1 ml, 0.015 mol) were added. The mixture was refluxed for 6 h and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol (yield **2a-c**, 45–94%).

Hydrolysis of β -(3-p-chlorophenoxyethyl-4-phenyl-5-thio-1,2,4-triazol-1-yl)propionitrile (2a) : (a) *Acid hydrolysis. Formation of amide 2b* : To a solution of nitrile **2a** (3.7 g; 0.01 mol), acetic acid-hydrochloric acid mixture (1 : 1; 10 ml) was added. After refluxing the mixture for 4 h, the solid product obtained was washed with water and crystallised from ethanol to give **2b** (1.77g, 45%), m.p. 130°.

(b) *Alkaline hydrolysis* : To a solution of nitrile **2a** (3.70 g, 0.01 mol) in ethanol (40 ml), was added NaOH (0.4 g,

0.01 mol). After heating the mixture for 3 h, it was cooled and acidified with dilute HCl and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol to give a product which was identified as the starting compound **1** by m.p., mnp, tlc and ir spectrum.

5-[2-(3-p-Chlorophenoxyethyl-4-phenyl-5-thio-1,2,4-triazol-1-ylethyl)-1',2',3',4'-IH-tetrazole (3): A mixture of the cyanoethyl derivative (**2a**; 1.67 g, 4.5 mmol), sodium azide (0.585 g, 9 mmol) and ammonium chloride (0.481 g, 9 mmol) in absolute dimethylformamide (40 ml) was heated at 120–30° for 18 h. After evaporation of the solvent under reduced pressure, the residue was dissolved in warm 5% KOH solution followed by filtration. The solid formed on acidification of the alkaline filtrate with dilute HCl to pH 2 was crystallised from aqueous ethanol as white crystals (0.48 g, 45%).

Dehydration of β -(3-p-chlorophenoxyethyl-4-phenyl-5-thio-1,2,4-triazol-1-yl)propionamide (2b). Formation of nitrile 2a: Treatment of the amide (**2b**; 3.88 g, 0.01 mol) with benzoyl chloride (1.2 ml, 0.01 mol) in dry benzene (30 ml) under reflux for 3 h, followed by cooling and crystallisation of the solid formed from ethanol yielded **2a** (2.25 g, 61%).

Reaction of the amide (2b) with secondary amines. Formation of the Mannich bases β -(3-p-chlorophenoxyethyl-4-phenyl-5-thio-1,2,4-triazol-1-yl)-N-piperidino/morpholinomethylpropionamide (4a,b): To a suspension of the amide (**2b**; 3.88 g, 0.01 mol) in ethanol (40 ml), a 37% formalin solution (0.9 ml, 0.03 mol) and piperidine or morpholine (0.01 mol) were added. After stirring of the reaction mixture for 3 h at room temperature in case of piperidine (or under reflux in case of morpholine) the formed solid was crystallised from proper solvent (yields 67–76%).

1-[β -(3'-p-Chlorophenoxyethyl-4'-phenyl-5'-thio-1',2',4'-triazol-1'-yl)propionyl]-3-phenylthiourea (5): Phenyl isothiocyanate (1.2 ml, 0.01 mol) was added to a boiling solution of amide **2b** (3.88 g, 0.01 mol) in ethanol (40 ml) and the mixture was refluxed for 6 h, then kept overnight at room temperature. The formed solid was crystallised from ethanol as colourless crystals (3.4 g, 65%).

β -(3-p-Chlorophenoxyethyl-4-phenyl-5-thio-1,2,4-triazol-1-yl)propionic acid (6): A mixture of the ester (**2c**; 0.01 mol) and NaOH (0.02 mol) in methanol (40 ml) was stirred at room temperature for 3 h. It was then filtered and the filtrate was acidified with dilute HCl. The resulting solid was washed with cold water and crystallised from water as colourless needles (65%).

β -(3-p-Chlorophenoxyethyl-4-phenyl-5-thio-1,2,4-triazol-1-yl)propionic acid hydrazide (7): To a solution **2c** (0.005 mol) in ethanol (40 ml), hydrazine hydrate (0.5 ml, 0.01 mol) was added. After heating the mixture under re-

flux for 6 h, the formed solid was crystallised (90%).

Condensation of 7 with aldehydes. Formation of β -(3-p-chlorophenoxyethyl-4-phenyl-5-thio-1,2,4-triazol-1-yl)propionylbenzal/p-chloro, p-methoxy and p-nitrobenzal-hydrazone (8a-d): A mixture of the hydrazide (**7**; 0.01 mol), aldehyde (0.01 mol) and catalytic amount of conc. HCl in ethanol (30 ml) was refluxed for 6 h. On cooling, the solid product formed was washed with cold ethanol and crystallised from proper solvent (yields 56–80%).

1-[β -(3'-p-Chlorophenoxyethyl-4'-phenyl-5'-thiotriazol-1-yl)propionyl]-4-phenylthiosemicarbazide (9): Reaction of hydrazide **7** (0.01 mol) with phenyl isothiocyanate (0.01 mol) under the same condition described above for compound **5** gave the product **9** (82%).

(B) Alkylation reaction products and their derivative:

Reaction of triazole 1 with halo compounds. Formation of derivatives 10a-d: To a solution of triazole **1** in ethanol (30 ml) containing triethylamine (0.015 mol), halo compounds (allyl bromide, chloroacetamide, chloroacetic acid, ethyl chloroacetate 0.01 mol) was added, in case of using chloroacetic acid and its ester as the alkylating agents, 0.02 and 0.01 mol NaOH were used respectively instead of triethylamine. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 6 h (or warmed for 10 min in case of ester **10d**), cooled and the product obtained directly (or after acidification the free acid **10c**) was filtered off and crystallised from proper solvent to give **10a-d** (yields 60–95%).

3-p-Chlorophenoxyethyl-4-phenyl-1,2,4-triazol-5-ylthioacetyl hydrazine (11): It was obtained by the reported method³, yield 91%, m.p. 70° (lit. 69°).

1-(3'-p-Chlorophenoxyethyl-4'-phenyl-1',2',4'-triazole-5'-thioacetyl)-4-phenylthiosemicarbazide (12): Treatment of **11** (0.01 mol) with phenyl isothiocyanate (0.01 mol) in ethanol (40 ml) under reflux for 6 h, followed by cooling, filtration and crystallisation gave **12** (76%).

N-Benzoyl/benzene sulphonyl-3-p-chlorophenoxyethyl-4-phenyl-1,2,4-triazol-5-ylthioacetylhydrazine (13, 14): Treatment of the hydrazide (**11**; 0.01 mol) with benzoyl chloride or benzene sulphonyl chloride (0.01 mol) in ethanol (60 ml, in case of benzoyl chloride) or in chloroform (40 ml, in case of benzene sulphonyl chloride) under reflux for 6 h (in case of benzoyl chloride) or under stirring at room temperature for 3 h (in case of benzene sulphonyl chloride), yielded solid that crystallised from proper solvent to give **13** or **14** (70 or 80%).

(C) Reaction of carboxymethylthiotriazole derivative (10c):

3-p-Chlorophenoxyethyl-4-phenyl-1,2,4-triazole-5-ylthioacetyl-DL-valine ethyl ester (15a): A mixture of DL-valine ethyl ester hydrochloride (0.001 mol) in acetonitrile (6 ml) containing triethylamine (0.01 mol), **10c** (0.001 mol) and dicyclohexylcarbodiimide (0.001 mol) was stirred at

0° for 1 h, at 5°. For another hour and at room temperature for 8 h. The reaction mixture was set aside overnight, the precipitate dicyclohexyl urea was filtered off, and the filtrate was evaporated under reduced pressure. The remaining residue was dissolved in ethyl acetate, filtered and the filtrate was washed with 1N HCl and saturated NaCl solution and dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. After evaporation of the solvent under reduced pressure, the remaining residue was triturated with light petrol (b.p. 40–60°) to afford a solid which on crystallisation gave **15a** (69%).

3-p-Chlorophenoxymethyl-4-phenyl-1,2,4-triazol-5-ylthioacetyl-L-leucine (15b) : A cold solution (–5°) of **10c** (0.02 mol), triethylamine (0.02 mol) and ethyl chloroformate (0.02 mol) in dry toluene was stirred for 30 minute. After the addition of a solution of L-leucine (0.02 mol) in KOH (1N, 20 ml), the stirring was continued for 3 h followed by extraction with ether. The aqueous phase was acidified with dilute HCl and the resulting solid was washed with water and crystallised to give **15b** (52%).

N-(3-p-Chlorophenoxymethyl-4-phenyl-1,2,4-triazole-5-ylthioacetyl)glycine/6-aminopenicillanic acid (15c,d) : To a solution of **10c** (0.01 mol) in benzene (25 ml), thionyl chloride (0.05 mol) was added and the mixture was refluxed for 7 h. The solution was then evaporated under reduced pressure and the residue obtained triturated with dry benzene with subsequent evaporation. This step was repeated several times to ensure complete removal of the excess thionyl chloride. To the solution of the formed acid chloride in benzene (20 ml) the amino component (glycine or 6-aminopenicillanic acid, 0.01 mol) in NaOH (1N; 10 ml) was added at 0° dropwise under stirring. After stirring the reaction mixture for 3 h at room temperature, it was extracted with benzene, the aqueous layer cooled to 0° and acidified with 0.1 N HCl to pH 3. The resulting solid was crystallised, to yield **15c/d** (61/55%).

2-(3-p-Chlorophenoxymethyl-4-phenyl-1',2',4'-triazol-5'-ylmercaptomethyl)-5-amino-1,3,4-thiadiazole (16) : A

mixture of thiosemicarbazide (0.012 mol), **10c** and phosphorus oxychloride (0.02 mol) was refluxed on a water-bath for 3 h. After cooling the reaction mixture was poured in cold NaOH solution (pH 8–9) and the resulting solid was washed with water and crystallised from ethanol to yield **16** (72%).

3-(3-p-Chlorophenoxymethyl-4-phenyl-1',2',4'-triazol-5'-ylmercaptomethyl)-4-aminothio-1,2,4-triazole (17) : A mixture of equimolar amounts of **10c** and thiocarbonylhydrazide was heated on a oil-bath at 160–65° for 1 h. On cooling, the solid product was crystallised from ethanol giving **17** (60%).

Preparation of metal complexes : A mixture of ethanolic solution of the amide (**2b**; 0.02 mol) and aqueous solution of the metal salt (0.01 mol) was refluxed for 4–6 h. The resulting solid was washed successively with excess of water, hot ethanol, and ether, then dried under reduced pressure. Metal content of the complexes was estimated by titration against EDTA solution using murexide indicator.

References

1. B. ZEEH, N. GOETZ, E. AMMERMAN and E. H. POMMER, Ger. Pat. 2 926, 280/ 1981 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1981, **94**, 192348); R. B. PATHAK, B. JAHAN and S. C. BAHREL, *Bokin Bobat*, 1980, **8**, 149 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1981, **94**, 306604); K. F. MODI, N. H. J. KRISHNAKUMAR, A. C. PADHYA and S. SOMASEKHARA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **54**, 741; P. C. WADE, B. R. VOGT and T. P. KISSICK, US Pat. 4 154 841/1979 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1979, **91**, 74655); D. A. BERGES, Ger. Pat. 2 742 726/1978 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1978, **89**, 24335).
2. J. J. AMICO, S. LYDIA and G. PETER, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1986, **23**, 1629; S. H. EL-TAMANY, M. E. ABDEL-FATTAH and M. EL-DEEN, *Indian. J. Chem., Sect. B*, communicated.
3. E. A. G. BAKHIT, M.Sc. Thesis, Assiut University, 1988.
4. M. H. ABO GHALIA, SALEM, M. EZZ EL-DIN, S. SHOEB and H. ZEDAN, *Pol. J. Chem.*, 1979, **53**, 2239.
5. E. SORKIN, W. ROTH and H. ERLNMEYER, *Helv. Chem. Acta*, 1952, **35**, 1736.
6. D. MURIA, A. L. J. COLE and J. L. WAIKER, *Planta. Med.*, 1982, **44**, 129.